

Student information:

Enosh Paul Niju

GH1026595

B141: Data Mining

**Healthcare Data set
recommendation system**

Introduction

One of the most precious commodities in this world if not the most is health. The datasets produced have helped to transform the landscape of healthcare research and development across the globe. We will be taking one of the such “Example” based on health data set and try to find solutions and hopefully by the end of this report have a clear idea about the two types of recommendation system that we have dealt with.

The codes are done on Databricks by using Pyspark. The type of file of dataset that is dealt with is a csv file.

Problem Statement:

To design and orchestrate two types of recommendation system using Databricks.

Data source:

The GitHub Link to the Project: <https://github.com/ENORIC/Data-Mining-Report-.git>

The data for this project was obtained from a site called Kaggle.com.

The link to the data set used in this project is:

(<https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/prasad22/healthcare-dataset>)

Development

The use of Apache pyspark on Databricks were the key components, for this conduction comprehensive analysis of the healthcare_dataset.

- By first initializing the Spark session

```
from pyspark.sql import SparkSession
```

- (DBFS) is the main data frame that is used as a layer cloud storage, which is used to store the raw CSV file.
- All the codes will be done in the cells of the Notebooks created within the folder

1. Upload healthcare_dataset.csv to DBFS inside a folder that is created in your database workspace, and it will be stored at something like this

```
"dbfs:/FileStore/Recommendations_for_Hospital_datasets/healthcare_dataset.csv"
```

2. Within the Folder create five notebooks in total and that are:

- Data Exploration
- Data Preprocessing
- Data Visualization
- Recommendation system 1
- Recommendation system 2

Setup

For every notebook in the folder the first cell will possess the important libraries that are needed for operating and the functioning of the codes.

```
#Importing all the necessary dependencies.

# Load healthcare dataset
df = spark.read.csv("dbfs://FileStore/Recommendations_for_Hospital_datasets/healthcare_dataset.csv", header=True,
inferSchema=True)

# For data loading and basic transformations
from pyspark.sql import SparkSession
from pyspark.sql.functions import col, count, when, isnan, lit

#Collect values from the Data set and sort
from pyspark.sql.functions import collect_list, col, count

from pyspark.sql.functions import collect_set, countDistinct, size

#Returns a column of distinct column
from pyspark.sql.functions import countDistinct

# For feature engineering
from pyspark.ml.feature import StringIndexer, IndexToString

# For evaluation (if needed)
from pyspark.ml.evaluation import RegressionEvaluator

# For visualization
import pandas as pd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

#For Recommendation system
from pyspark.sql.functions import lit
from pyspark.ml.feature import StringIndexer
from pyspark.ml.recommendation import ALS

from pyspark.sql.functions import concat_ws, col, row_number
from pyspark.sql.window import Window
from pyspark.ml import Pipeline
from pyspark.ml.feature import Tokenizer, StopWordsRemover, HashingTF, IDF, BucketedRandomProjectionLSH
```

As you see in the figure above the necessary dependencies have to be imported.

Chapter 1: Data Exploration

- Overview of the data set:
This dataset comprises of patient health records that captures crucial, diagnostic, therapeutic as well as administrative details.

The key attributes are:

- Name
- Age
- Gender
- Blood Type
- Medical Condition
- Date of Admission
- Doctor
- Hospital
- Insurance Provider
- Billing Amount
- Room Number
- Admission Type
- Discharge Date
- Medication
- Test Results

Starting the data exploration first by inspecting the Schema of the data set. As shown in the figure below the code has exhibited the column names as well as the data type of each column, by this we can understand what kind of Dataset we will be dealing with and how we can manipulate the data.

```

print("Column Names:")
print(df.columns)

# Schema data types of each column
print("\nSchema:")
df.printSchema()

['Name', 'Age', 'Gender', 'Blood Type', 'Medical Condition', 'Date of Admission', 'Doctor', 'Hospital', 'Insurance Provider', 'Billing Amount', 'Room Number', 'Admission Type', 'Discharge Date', 'Medication', 'Test Results']

Schema:
root
 |-- Name: string (nullable = true)
 |-- Age: integer (nullable = true)
 |-- Gender: string (nullable = true)
 |-- Blood Type: string (nullable = true)
 |-- Medical Condition: string (nullable = true)
 |-- Date of Admission: date (nullable = true)
 |-- Doctor: string (nullable = true)
 |-- Hospital: string (nullable = true)
 |-- Insurance Provider: string (nullable = true)
 |-- Billing Amount: double (nullable = true)
 |-- Room Number: integer (nullable = true)
 |-- Admission Type: string (nullable = true)
 |-- Discharge Date: date (nullable = true)
 |-- Medication: string (nullable = true)
 |-- Test Results: string (nullable = true)

```

The next code proceeds to show a sample schema as well as the preview of the dataset.

```

# Show schema and preview
df.printSchema()
df.show(15)

```

Insurance Provider	Room Number	Admission Type	Discharge Date	Medication	Test Results
dicare	19580.87234486093	Emergency	2020-11-15	Paracetamol	Inconclusive
CHRISTINA MARTINEZ	20	A+	2021-12-28	Cancer	Suzanne Thomas Powell Robinson a...
Cigna	45820.46272159459	Emergency	2022-01-07	Paracetamol	Inconclusive
JASMIINE aGuILaR	82	Male	2020-07-01	Asthma	Daniel Ferguson Sons Rich and
Cigna	50119.222791548505	Elective	2020-07-14	Aspirin	Abnormal
CHRISTOPHER BERG	58	Female	2021-05-23	Cancer	Heather Day Padilla-Walker UnitedHeal
thcare	19784.63106221073	Elective	2021-06-22	Paracetamol	Inconclusive
mIchElLe daniELs	72	Male	2020-04-19	Cancer	John Duncan Schaefer-Porter Me
dicare	12576.795609050234	Urgent	2020-04-22	Paracetamol	Normal
aaRon MARtiNeZ	38	Female	2023-08-13	Hypertension	Douglas Mayo Lyons-Blair Me
dicare	7999.586879604188	Urgent	2023-09-05	Lipitor	Inconclusive
connOR HANsEn	75	Female	2019-12-12	Diabetes	Kenneth Fletcher Powers Miller, an...
Cigna	43282.28335770435	Emergency	2019-12-28	Penicillin	Abnormal
rObErT bAuer	68	Female	2020-05-22	Asthma	Theresa Freeman Rivera-Gutierrez UnitedHeal
thcare	33207.706633729606	Urgent	2020-06-19	Lipitor	Normal
bR00kE brady	44	Female	2021-10-08	Cancer	Roberta Stewart Morris-Arellano UnitedHeal
thcare	40701.599227308754	Urgent	2021-10-13	Paracetamol	Normal

only showing top 15 rows

One of the main topics to cover was the summary statistics and it is most sensible to do the summary statistics on the attributes Age and Billing amount, which can be able to deduce the min and the max age as well as the mean of the age of patients that are admitted to these hospitals. Billing costs can also show the average amount of fee that is paid to these hospitals by the patients.

```

df.describe(["Age"]).show()
df.describe(["Billing Amount"]).show()

```

To know the Most used medication and the least used medication by the patients:

```
df.select(
    max("medication").alias("Most_Used_Medication"),
    min("medication").alias("Least_Used_Medication")
).show()
```

To give an idea of how many types of distinct count in each of the columns are:

```
for col_name in df.columns:
    distinct_count=df.select(col_name).distinct().count()
    print(f'{col_name}: {distinct_count}')
```

To know if there is any null values that need to be dropped

```
from pyspark.sql.functions import col, count, when

df.select([count(when(col(c).isNull(), c)).alias(c) for c in df.columns]).show()
```

The purpose of this dataset is also to find the most common medical condition and if you find any similarity of medical conditions for that we would need to know how many types of medical conditions are there in this dataset:

```
df.groupBy("Medical Condition").count().orderBy("count",
ascending=False).show(15, truncate=False)
```

Now to find the common medications that is common to treat all the medical conditions of each patient.

```
# Find medications that is common with more than one medical condition
shared_meds = df.select("Medical Condition", "Medication") \
    .dropna() \
    .distinct() \
    .groupBy("Medication") \
    .agg(count("Medical Condition").alias("Number_of_conditions")) \
    .filter("Number_of_conditions > 1") \
    .orderBy("Number_of_conditions", ascending=False)
```

```

shared_meds.show(20, truncate=False)

#Patient-condition pairs
patient_conditions = df.select("Name", "Medical Condition") \
    .dropna() \
    .distinct()

#Count of unique conditions each patient has
condition_count = patient_conditions.groupBy("Name") \
    .agg(count("Medical Condition").alias("Condition_count")) \
    .filter("Condition_count > 1")

condition_count.show(10, truncate=False)

#Getting Each patient's conditions along with medications used for them
condition_summary_with_meds = df.select("Name", "Medical Condition",
"Medication") \
    .dropna() \
    .distinct() \
    .groupBy("Name") \
    .agg(
        count("Medical Condition").alias("Condition_count"),
        collect_set("Medical Condition").alias("Conditions"),
        collect_set("Medication").alias("Medications")
    ) \
    .filter("Condition_count > 1") \
    .orderBy("Condition_count", ascending=False)

condition_summary_with_meds.show(10, truncate=False)

```

The rest of the few codes also shows in the notebook about the most frequent doctors that appear in the dataset and also one of the more interesting topic was to check the patients that visits multiple doctors as well as the count of doctors they visit.

```

# Distinct patient-doctor pairs
patient_doctors = df.select("Name", "Doctor") \
    .dropna() \
    .distinct()

# Patients with more than one distinct doctor
patients_multiple_doctors = patient_doctors.groupBy("Name") \
    .agg(countDistinct("Doctor").alias("doctor_count")) \
    .filter("doctor_count > 1") \
    .select("Name")

# Join to get doctors for those patients
patients_and_doctors = patients_multiple_doctors.join(patient_doctors,
on="Name") \
    .groupBy("Name") \
    .agg(
        collect_set("Doctor").alias("Doctors")
    ) \
    .orderBy("Name")

patients_and_doctors =
patients_and_doctors.withColumn("Number_of_Doctors", size("Doctors")) \
    .orderBy("Number_of_Doctors", ascending=False)

patients_and_doctors.show(truncate=False, n=20)

```

The rest of the notebook also deals with the question of how many patients are in each respective hospital and upon inspection the code was able to find out the highest patients count being 44 was in LLC Smith hospital. Along with that we were also able to find the count of patient gender proportion and show an interesting outlook on what are the common medical conditions between the two genders

```

df.groupBy("Gender", "Medical Condition").count().\
orderBy("count", ascending=False).show(20, truncate=False)

```

Another code also showed the top medications per medical conditions.

```

df.groupBy("Medical Condition", "Medication").count().\
orderBy("count", ascending=False).show(20, truncate=False)

```

Data Preprocessing

In data preprocessing we will be dealing with the following.

1. Checking if there are any missing values through each column
2. Handling the missing values
3. Dropping unnecessary columns
4. Handling Patient names, Duplicates and inconsistent data.

To check if there are null values or missing values in the given dataset. As per the observation the output shows “0” “Null” values. Also running a code to see if at all there any null values in any of the rows we drop it in order to clean it and upon observation there is no difference before and after the cleaning process.

```
for col_name in df.columns:  
    null_count = df.filter(df[col_name].isNull()).count()  
    print(f'Column '{col_name}' has {null_count} null values")
```

```
critical_cols = ["Name", "Doctor", "Hospital", "Medication"]  
  
df_clean = df.dropna(subset=critical_cols)  
  
print(f"Row count before cleaning: {df.count()}")  
print(f"Row count after cleaning: {df_clean.count()}")
```

In this health care data set, room number is considered to be insignificant and can be neglected hence it was best to drop the column from the data set.

```
# Drop the "Room Number" column  
df = df.drop("Room Number")  
  
# Show new schema  
df.printSchema()
```

The rest of the notebook shows how to remove duplicates in case of typos, preventing multiple rows of patients that have similar names as they were treated as the same person. Along with filling missing values in those non-critical columns.

Data Visualization

In Data Visualization we will be tackling on how we could interpret this dataset to it's maximum potential. Data Visualization would help us to find patterns, outliers or any trends that can be read easily by human in form of a visual context and it can be through any sort of graphs, pie chart, histograms, etc. making it quite efficient for the dataset to be interpreted. Finding Answers to the questions like:

1. The age distribution of Patients in the hospital

Please refer to the code in the notebook. The figure above shows the age distribution of the patients in the various hospitals given in the dataset. The "Y" axis showing the number of patients the with distinct age groups along with "X" axis. Upon interpretation the graph shoes a relatively high patient count as respective to age that is under the group of 66 and above (Senior Citizens) making it the highest age distribution compared to the mere 116 patient count of age group between 0-17 (Children).

2. “Top 10’s Graphs”: Consulting Doctors, Hospitals by Patient Volume, Most Prescribed Medication

- As you see from the graph below (Fig. A) Michael Smith is the most consulted doctor by the patients among the rest of the top 10 doctors, peaking the highest at 27.
- From the graph below (Fig. B) LLC Smith peaks at the heighest showing that there are around at least 44 patients that have been admitted, treated or recorded. Compared to the rest of the hospitals in the graph
- (Fig. c) that final graph of the “Top 10’s Graphs” shows the top 5 prescribed medicines, and from the graph one can be able to deduce that “Lipitor” is the most prescribed medicine but there are not much significant gaps between the rest of the of 4 medicines in the list.

(Fig. A)

(Fig. B)

(Fig. C)

3. Age diversity analysis based on frequency:

The data includes patients with a wide age range, mainly from about 15 to 85 years old.

High frequency in some age groups: There seems to be a higher concentration of patients in certain age groups, forming peaks in the graph.

“Specifically, the age groups of 20-30, 35-45, 45-55, 55-65, and 70-80 have a large number of patients”.

“Low number of patients in the very young and very old age groups: The number of patients under 15 years old and over 85 years old is relatively low.”

The age distribution is uneven, suggesting that there may be “specific factors influencing hospitalization” in different age groups or that this is a characteristic of the population being studied.

4. Analysis of Test Results (BMI Classification) "The pie chart of test results (which may be BMI classification based on the annotations "Abnormal", "Normal", "Inconclusive")" shows: Evenly distributed among groups: Abnormal: 33.54% Normal: 33.35% Inconclusive: 33.11% The test results are fairly evenly divided into three groups. "This may imply that in the studied population, the proportion of people with normal, abnormal and inconclusive test results is similar"

Recommendation System 1: Collaborative Filtering

This recommendation system, to be specific is based on User-Item Matrix.

To develop a code for suggested feedback on which type of medication to be used for each patient. The code would give an output of the top 3 recommended medication for the patient. In the output table the column "Preference" shows the "Predicted confidence score" so the doctors can prescribe the medicines that have a higher confidence score.

In this recommendation system we will be using “implicit feedback” system as the patient, or the medication have no real “actual rating or scores” of any sort hence we would indicate a rating = 1.0 to show there is some kind of interaction that happened.

This recommendation system is particularly useful for recommending the incoming patients based on their own or the medication history of other patients and give them a recommended medication for their stated medical condition. This would also be helpful for exploring pattern analysis. Upon executing the code the output, we got is The first table shows the top 5 preferred medication along with the confidence points to show which one is the most recommended one.

```
+-----+-----+-----+
|Name      |Medication |confidence |
+-----+-----+-----+
|AARON DuncAn|Paracetamol|0.9537239 |
|AARON DuncAn|Aspirin    |3.5613775E-6|
|AARON DuncAn|Ibuprofen  |3.1106174E-6|
|AARON DuncAn|Penicillin |1.9185245E-6|
|AARON DuncAn|Lipitor    |7.003546E-7 |
|AARON HicKS |Lipitor    |0.95431596 |
|AARON HicKS |Aspirin    |1.28299E-5 |
|AARON HicKS |Penicillin |6.403774E-6 |
|AARON HicKS |Ibuprofen  |5.759299E-6 |
|AARON HicKS |Paracetamol|7.376075E-7 |
+-----+-----+-----+
only showing top 10 rows
```

The Second table shows only the most preferred medication per patient that is confidence level closer to 1.0. Which is much more important for the recommendation.

```
+-----+-----+-----+
|Name           |Medication |confidence|
+-----+-----+-----+
|AARON DuncAn   |Paracetamol|0.9537239 |
|AARON Hicks    |Lipitor    |0.95431596|
|AARON bAlDWIN Jr.|Paracetamol|0.9537239 |
|AARON hAWkIns  |Penicillin |0.9543104 |
|AAROn HaRt     |Paracetamol|0.9537239 |
|AAROn wiLsON   |Aspirin    |0.9539244 |
|AARoN FOSTer   |Lipitor    |0.95431596|
|AARoN HOPkINs  |Paracetamol|0.9537239 |
|AARoN grEEEnE  |Aspirin    |0.9539244 |
|AARon OnEal    |Lipitor    |0.95431596|
+-----+-----+-----+
only showing top 10 rows
```

Recommendation System 2: Content Based

The important snippets of the code

This recommendation system is specifically based on TF-IDF Vectorization pipeline as well as using and LSH Model. The reason of choosing this feature extraction method is because the data set is a heavily text-based data. The Logic of TF-IDF is finding similarity of “rare” words of one patient to the other patients in the list. And extracting the specific characteristic similarity between the patients and displaying an output that can be useful. Let’s say in the code, we took the example of “karEN huNteR” one of the “rare” words that was used to find the similarity between the other patients was the medical condition of “Hypertension” and the output was able to point out the similar patients that are also diagnosed with “Hypertension” as shown below

```

Top Similar Patients to: karEN huNteR
+-----+-----+
|Name          |combined_text      |
+-----+-----+
|JILLiAn SteWART |elderly male o- hypertension inconclusive elective|
|HanNAh caMPBeLL DDs|elderly male o- hypertension inconclusive elective|
|abIgAil m00re   |elderly male o- hypertension inconclusive elective|
|RACHEl rHoDeS  |elderly male o- hypertension inconclusive elective|
|MAry mCkEE     |elderly male o- hypertension inconclusive elective|
|joaN walkER    |elderly male o- hypertension inconclusive elective|
|kAREN hunTer   |elderly male o- hypertension inconclusive elective|
|sAndy whITe    |elderly male o- hypertension inconclusive elective|
|LESLIe LEE     |elderly male o- hypertension inconclusive elective|
|RachEl GATEs   |elderly male o- hypertension inconclusive elective|
|dr. John MUeller|elderly male o- hypertension inconclusive elective|
|jeSSica cAmACHO|elderly male o- hypertension inconclusive elective|
|PAtricia R0drIGuEz|elderly male o- hypertension inconclusive elective|
|Joseph NGUYEN  |elderly male o- hypertension inconclusive elective|
|bryAn coOk     |elderly male o- hypertension inconclusive elective|
+-----+-----+

```

Through the code we were also able to find out Top recommended Medications, Doctors and hospital that is in respective to the patient over here “karEN huNteR”, the output showing the best percentage for the particular attribute stating that “these are the best options for the particular diagnosis of the patient base on the similarity”. As shown in the output below.

```

Top Recommended Medications:
+-----+-----+-----+
|Medication |count|percentage|
+-----+-----+-----+
|Aspirin    |4    |28.6      |
|Ibuprofen  |4    |28.6      |
|Paracetamol|3    |21.4      |
|Penicillin |3    |21.4      |
+-----+-----+-----+

```

Top Recommended Doctors:

Doctor	count	percentage
Steve Adams	1	7.1
Jasmine King	1	7.1
Gregory Holt	1	7.1
Barbara Brown	1	7.1
Brandon Glenn	1	7.1
Christopher Abbott	1	7.1
Joseph Fowler	1	7.1
Dr. Crystal Price	1	7.1
Amy Patel	1	7.1
Deborah Henderson	1	7.1
Lisa Brown	1	7.1
Diana Johnson	1	7.1
Walter Wagner	1	7.1
Jacob Wallace	1	7.1

Top Recommended Hospitals:

Hospital	count	percentage
Sellers Woods Burgess, and	1	7.1
Lee Inc	1	7.1
Thomas-Salinas	1	7.1
Group Roth	1	7.1
Ltd Henderson	1	7.1
and Valencia Rivera Vaughn,	1	7.1
Schmidt-Thomas	1	7.1
Hart-Ferguson	1	7.1
Dixon Smith and Jackson,	1	7.1
Group Nicholson	1	7.1
Hall-Griffin	1	7.1
Wright-Brown	1	7.1
Burns Allen, and Simon	1	7.1
Garrison and Palmer, Gallegos	1	7.1

As one can easily interpret that for the Patient “karEN huNteR”, in terms of the recommendation the best sequence for the patient solution would be

Medicine: Aspirin

Doctor: Any of the top 10 doctor as they all are the expertise for the patient’s cause.

Hospital: Any of the top 10 Hospitals as they offer the services for the patient’s cause

Conclusion

The Global health sector is one of the biggest sectors in the world that is projected to skyrocket to a value of 665.37 Billion dollars by the year of 2028(Benchmark international, 2024). Hence this can stretch the fact that how important is health to the society. And those huge amount of raw data alone cannot help the health sector to improve. It must be most structured, explored which would help to give more insights in the field. Answering interesting questions, finding patterns through analysis would help many health professionals to give the best services possible. As humans the best way to to interpret huge data is through visualization can interpreting huge data in the form of graphs makes it much more efficient.

Finally, everyone loves personalized care and to make any sort of industry profitable the best way is for layering the industry with recommendation system. Especially in the health industry it would allow the front-line workers with “data-driven guidance” for a more sort out solution to any sort of issues they would be faced and could diagnose the patients with the most optimal accuracy. These steps would boost the health sector to be more satisfactory, smarter and safer.

Reference List

- “2024 Global Healthcare & Medical Industry Report.” *Benchmark International*, 2024, www.benchmarkintl.com/de/insights/2024-global-healthcare-medical-industry-report/. Accessed 3 July 2025.
- “Community | Apache Spark.” *Spark.apache.org*, spark.apache.org/community.html.
- Kaggle. “Kaggle: Your Home for Data Science.” *Kaggle.com*, www.kaggle.com/.
- Medium. “Medium.” *Medium*, 2018, medium.com/.
- stackOverflow. “Newest Questions.” *Stack Overflow*, 2025, stackoverflow.com/questions.